
**NON-PARAMTRIC ESTIMATION FOR TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS' SURVIVAL
TIME USING INCOMPLETED OBSERVATION**

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ABSTRACT:

Background: In India, tuberculosis is a significant public health issue, but little study has looked at the effectiveness of treatment and patient survival rates. This study's objective was to look at the survival patterns of tuberculosis patients after a six-month course of treatment. To calculate the typical patient survival time for tuberculosis patients.

Methods: We examined the clinical trial data of 1237 tuberculosis patients enrolled in three different types of treatments, including a control regimen, that were each given for six months. A retrospective cohort study research design was used. Sputum conversion (positive to negative) is considered an event of interest during the treatment period. In a univariate descriptive statistics analysis, the log-rank test and the non-parametric Kaplan-Meier method were used to determine patient median survival times and assess variations in survival patterns across TB patients. The P value indicates a significant difference at the 5% threshold of significance, meaning that the male and female groups' survival periods are not equal. STATA 15.0 statistical software was used to analyse the data.

Results: 1062 occurrences were observed (85.6% of the total), while 175 observations (14.2%) were censored. The survival curves for control, treatment A, and treatment B in TB patients differ significantly from one another. There is a substantial difference between the survival curves of males and females among the various gender groups (log rank statistic = 16.606, Df = 1, P = 0.000), and (log rank statistic = 8.805, Df = 2, P = 0.012). (95%CI: 2.53-2.74), the mean overall survival (OS) was 62 days. Males had a mean survival time of 67 days (95% CI: 2.62-2.82), and females had a mean survival time of 64 days (95% CI: 2.17-2.49).

Conclusion: Patients with TB had a six-month survival time, as seen. Significant differences exist between the survival curves for males and females as well as between treatment groups. In terms of survival, males outnumber females. Compared to treatment A and the control treatment, treatment B has a higher survival rate.

Keyword: Kaplan Meier, Survival Time, Log Rank test, Kaplan Meier curve and TB Patients.

INTRODUCTION TB:

The number of deaths from TB will reach 1.5 million worldwide by 2020. (Including 214 000 HIV-positive people). In 2020, 1.1 million children around the world developed TB. Medical

professionals sometimes ignore vulnerable patient TB because it can be hard to diagnose and cure. Two-thirds of the total is made up of eight nations, with India leading the list, followed by China, Indonesia and Philippines. According to the most recent national TB patient cost study, costs for roughly one out of every two TB-affected homes globally surpass 20% of household income. The target of having no TB patients or their households incur catastrophic costs as a result of the disease by 2020 was not accomplished.

TB CURRENT STATUS IN INDIA:

The overall number of TB patients in 2021 was 19,333,81. It was 16,28,1611 in 2020. The death rate from tuberculosis of all types increased by 11% in India between 2019 and 2020. Of the 21,35,830 individuals diagnosed with TB in 2021, TB-related therapy was started in 20, 30,509 of them. In 2020, 83% of the patients who were notified had successful therapy, while 4% died while undergoing it.

In India, the prevalence of all kinds of tuberculosis was 312 per lakh persons in 2021. The highest prevalence was found in Delhi (747 per one lakh people), while the lowest was found in Gujarat. The predicted number of tuberculosis cases in India for 2020, according to this data, was 188 per 1 lakh people. Childhood tuberculosis is still a major issue in India. It accounts for approximately 31% of the global burden. Children account for 6-7% of all treated patients under the National Tuberculosis Elimination Program (NTEP) throughout the last decade.

SURVIVAL ANALYSIS:

Assume T is the amount of time before a facility defaults. T's unpredictability can be expressed in three ways, as explained by Kalbfleisch and Prentice [1980] and Leemis [1995]: The survival function, sometimes abbreviated S, is the principal focus of attention. It is defined as

$$S(t) = Pr Pr (T > t) \quad \dots (1)$$

Where Pr is the probability and T is a random variable that represents the time of death, t is a time variable. In other words, the probability that the time to death is later than t is the survival function. The complement of the survival function is the lifespan distribution function, commonly abbreviated as F.

$$F(t) = Pr Pr (T \leq t) = 1 - S(t) \quad \dots (2)$$

If F is differentiable, the derivative—the density function of the lifespan distribution—which is what, is typically referred to as f,

$$f(t) = F'(t) = \frac{d}{dt} F(t) \quad \dots (3)$$

The event rate at time t conditional on survival until time t or later (that is T t) is defined as the hazard function.

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{Pr Pr (t \leq T < t + dt)}{dt \cdot S(t)} = \frac{F(t)}{S(t)} = -\frac{S'(t)}{S(t)} \quad \dots (4)$$

An alternative definition of it is;

$$\Lambda(t) = -\log S(t) \quad \dots (5)$$

The amount of time until death at a given time t_0 , assuming survival to that age, is known as the future lifetime. As a result, it is $T - t_0$ in the notation used today. The value of the anticipated future lifetime is the projected future lifetime. Given that one survives till the age of t_0 , the likelihood of dying at or before that age $t_0 + t$ is;

Function of distribution $F(t)$ is defined as the chance that the time to event (T) is shorter or equal to a specified time (t).

$$Pr Pr (T_{i,l} \leq t_0 + \frac{t}{T} > t_0) = \frac{Pr Pr (t_0 < T \leq t_0 + t)}{Pr Pr (T > t_0)} = \frac{F(t + t_0) - F(t_0)}{S(t_0)} \dots (6)$$

As a result, the future lifetime probability density is,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{F(t+t_0)-F(t_0)}{S(t_0)} = \frac{f(t+t_0)}{S(t_0)} \dots (7)$$

And the anticipated future lifespan is stated as,

$$\frac{1}{S(t_0)} \int_0^{\infty} t f(t + t_0) dt = \frac{1}{S(t_0)} \int_0^{\infty} S(t) dt \dots (8)$$

KAPLAN-MEIER SURVIVAL ESTIMATE

The phrase "Kaplan Meier" stems from the names of two statisticians, Paul Meier and Edward L. Kaplan, who collaborated and published a paper in 1958 on how to handle time-to-event data. In order to count the number of patients who survive medical treatment, they created the Kaplan-Meier estimator. Later, the analysis of data in cohort studies was improved by the use of survival statistics and Kaplan-Meier curves estimations. In order to compare two research populations and describe the survivorship of a study population, Kaplan-Meier (KM), a nonparametric estimate of the survival function, is frequently utilized.

One of the finest statistical techniques for calculating the likelihood that a patient will survive after receiving treatment for a specific period of time is the KM estimate. It uses a straightforward graphical presenting strategy. The intervention effect in clinical trials or community trials is measured over time by counting the number of participants who were saved or survived following the intervention. The easiest method for figuring out survival over time is a KM estimate, regardless of the challenges posed by the individuals or circumstances. The Kaplan Meier estimate uses curves to calculate the events, censoring, and survival probability.

In epidemiology, the Kaplan-Meier survival curve is used to compare two groups of people and analyse time-to-event data. The percentage of patients that survive a certain event, like death, over a predetermined amount of time is calculated using the survival curve. The statistical difference in survival rates between two groups of patients or subjects can also be calculated.

Given both filtered and unfiltered observed survival periods, the KM (or product-limit) technique can be used to estimate the survival probability non-parametrically. Assume that events occur in k patients at varying intervals throughout the follow-up period time, $t_1 < t_2 < t_3 < t_4 < t_5 \dots < t_k$. The probabilities of surviving from one interval to the next can be multiplied together

to obtain the cumulative survival probability because it is assumed that events occur independently of one another. The probability of being alive at time t_j , $S(t_j)$, is calculated using $S(t_{j-1})$, the probability of being alive at time t_{j-1} , n_j the number of patients living just before t_j , and d_j , the number of events t_j ,

$$S(t_j) = S(t_{j-1}) \left(1 - \frac{d_j}{n_j}\right)$$

Where $t_0 = 0$ and $S(0) = 1$. Since is constant between event times.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The Kaplan-Meier technique has the benefit of taking censoring-the omission of a patient from follow-up-into account. According to Patrick Schober and Thomas R. Vetter (2018)⁽¹⁾, a Kaplan-Meier curve is a useful graphical tool for illustrating the estimated survival function. The Kaplan-Meier technique assesses the uncorrected likelihood of living past a particular point in time. The popular log-rank test can only be used for quick, unadjusted comparisons when comparing survival curves between groups. We developed the Kaplan Meier product limit method and showed the medical community how to use imperfect observation data in 1958, in partnership with L. Kaplan and Paul Meier.

These statistical models, developed by Ritesh Singh and Keshab Mukhopadhyay in (2011)⁽²⁾, compare the cumulative likelihood of events across time for two or more cohorts while accounting for other important variables. This article exposes the reader to commonly used survival analysis topics and covers the fundamentals of survival analysis.

Prabhakar Mishra, Uday C. Ghoshal, and Sushmita Rai (2021)⁽³⁾, Comparing survival curves, analysing time-to-event data patterns, figuring out why data might be suppressed, figuring out how explanatory variables and survival time relate in survival analysis, a variety of regression models are available that can take any number of covariates (categorical or continuous) into account and produce adjusted hazard ratios for specific components. The 257 tuberculosis patients, who were randomly assigned to one of four treatments, including a control regimen, for an equal amount of time, provided the data for this application. The time to sputum smear conversion (from positive to negative) during the therapy phase is significant. Only 12.5% of the 257 patients had censored observations, although 87.5% had really witnessed the relevant event. Gender and treatment. Tsehay Haile, Kasim Mohammed and Endeshaw Assefa (2021)⁽⁴⁾, the Kaplan-Meier method was used to estimate survival time, and the Cox regression model was used to find characteristics that had a statistically significant impact on how long TB patients lived. The authors examined the analytical techniques that were used.

The statistical test for the treatment-time interaction is of borderline significance, and such a post-hoc (data-driven) study is debatable, according to TG Clark, M.J. Bradburn, SB Love, and DG Altman's (2003)⁽⁵⁾ discussion of the cancer patients' incomplete observation data. Therefore, rather of relying on occurrences that occurred after a given time point, the overall conclusion must be based on the entire follow-up. The Kaplan-Meier technique has the benefit of taking censoring-the omission of a patient from follow-up-into account. According to Patrick Schober and Thomas

R. Vetter (2018)⁽⁶⁾, a Kaplan-Meier curve is a useful graphical tool for illustrating the estimated survival function. The Kaplan-Meier technique assesses the uncorrected likelihood of living past a particular point in time. The popular log-rank test can only be used for quick, unadjusted comparisons when comparing survival curves between groups. We developed the Kaplan Meier product limit method and showed the medical community how to use imperfect observation data in 1958, in partnership with L. Kaplan and Paul Meier.

The study paper by Shankar Prinja, Nidhi Gupta, and Ramesh Verma (2010)⁽⁷⁾, focuses on ideas in survival analysis methodologies, notions of censoring in clinical trials, non-parametric for Kaplan Meier, and the parametric distribution how to deal with the censoring data. The identification of change-points in survival curves and an estimate of where they are located find significant use in clinical research, according to Xuan Chen and Michael Baron's (2014)⁽⁸⁾ work. The approach of least squares combined with the Kaplan-Meier survival function estimator results in a more effective process. These statistical models, developed by Ritesh Singh and Keshab Mukhopadhyay in (2011)⁽⁹⁾, compare the cumulative likelihood of events across time for two or more cohorts while accounting for other important variables. This article exposes the reader to commonly used survival analysis topics and covers the fundamentals of survival analysis. The Kaplan-Meier approach is only a way of creating survival curves as a function of time, giving an immediate understanding of the clinical phenomenon being researched. Graziella DArrigo, Daniela Leonardis, Samar Abd ElHafeez, Maria Fusaro, Giovanni Tripepi, and Stefanos Roumeliotis (2021)⁽¹⁰⁾. A Kaplan-Meier curve plots time on the abscissa axis and cumulative survival on the ordinate axis.

Rukayya Alkassim, Sulaiman Abubakar, and Lker Etikan (2017)⁽¹¹⁾, we discussed the Kaplan-Meier statistical method, which is very useful in the investigation of time-to-event data in the field of epidemiology. To assess patients who have attained a particular event and those who have been censored over a particular time period, the procedure is employed in survival analysis. In comparing groups of people, such as control and treatment groups, it is also helpful. Diagnosed, according to the multivariate analysis of the Cox regression model. Dr. Geeta Pardeshi (2009)⁽¹²⁾, every technical detail the overall estimate of patients still alive at the end of each month was obtained using the Kaplan-Meier curve. The changes in survival patterns over time among diverse groups were examined using the log rank test. The Cox proportional hazards model was used in multivariate analysis to identify death risk factors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The data came from a TB-related retrospective cohort research. The data contained in this application were collected from 1237 tuberculosis patients who participated in a three-treatment, six-month trial at the National Institute for Research in Tuberculosis (ICMR) in Chennai, India. STATA statistical software was used to examine the data.

MATERIAL

Split-drug regimens are a novel approach in this study for treating patients with pulmonary tuberculosis identified by sputum smear. P.551-458 in *Tropical Medicine and International Health*, Chinese Journal of Medical Genetics

9, 2004. The pertinent event is when sputum turns from positive to negative during treatment. There were 1062 total events, of which 85.8% were cases that underwent the event of interest defined as cases that developed disease during the treatment period (6 months)—and 175 (14.2%) were censored observations.

1. Age - The patients admitted in the age group between 9 to 68 years.
2. Sputum Culture (Status at End of Treatment (6m))
 - (i). Censored – (0) All Negative cases consistently
 - (ii). Event – (1)
3. Event - (i) Positive to negative sputum conversion – (1)
 - (ii) Censored as code – (0)
4. Time (in Months).

The event is coded as 1, whereas censorship is labelled as 0. The data set is used to empirically examine the survival difference between two treatment groups under various model assumptions.

RESULTS:

Table 1. Description of event of interest with Treatment Groups

Summary Statistics				
Treatment Group	N	No of Events	Censored	
			N	Percent
Control	407	355	52	12.8%
Treatment A	415	369	46	11.1%
Treatment B	415	338	77	18.6%
Overall	1237	1062	175	14.1%

Our study included 1237 people in total. There were 1062 (14.1%) participants who experienced an event of interest (positive to negative), and three different treatment types were taken into consideration: control groups, trial 1 (treatment A), and trial II. Of the 407 control groups, 355 (87.22%) were censored. 46 (11.1%) of the 369 events of interest from Trial I was censored. In Trial II, the event interest was 338 (81.44%) and was incomplete or did not convert to positive or negative 77 (18.6%).

Table 2. Sputum Conversation classifications According Age

Status of Sputum Culture Conversion				
Age	Status	N	f	%
Less than 25	Not Converted	1237	44	10.9
	Converted		361	89.1

	Total	405	100
25 to 40	Not Converted	88	16.5
	Converted	444	83.5
	Total	532	100
More than 40	Not Converted	43	14.3
	Converted	257	85.7
	Total	300	100

Compared to other age groups, young patients have better results for sputum conversion from positive to negative.

Table 3. Patients Survivor function for treatment

Treatment Group	Mean	Std. Error	95% CI	
			LL	UL
Treatment A	2.589	0.078	2.437	2.742
Treatment B	2.484	0.071	2.345	2.624
Control	2.801	0.082	2.639	2.962
Overall	2.624	0.045	2.537	2.712

The control groups had a greater median survival rate when compared to treatments A and B. Treatment A has a mean survival time of 2.589 (S.E = 0.078), Treatment B has a mean survival time of 2.484 (S.E. 0.071), and the control regimen has a mean survival time of 2.801 (S.E. = 0.082). It shows that control treatments have a longer survival time for the incident than treatment A and B. Non-parametric tests, however, reveal a substantial difference between these three treatment groups.

Figure-1.0 Kaplan Meier step method for TB patients according to treatments

Figure-1.1 Kaplan Meier curves for TB patients according to Treatments

The graph above presents the plots of the Kaplan-Meier curves for three groups: control, treatment A, and treatment B. The control group's Kaplan Meier curve is consistently higher than the KM curves for treatment A and treatment B. These results show that the treatment group, which is the control group, has a higher prognosis for survival than treatments A and B. implying that the treatment's benefits over the control group increase as event.

Table 4. Description of event of interest and censored for Gender

Sex	Total (N)	No of Events	Censored	
			N	%
Female	313	281	32	10.20%
Male	924	781	143	15.50%
Overall	1237	1062	175	14.10%

Out of 313 female participants, 281 (89.77%) and 32 (10.20%) had sputum conversion (positive to negative) events of interest. A total of 924 males had events of interest in sputum conversion: 781 (84.52%) and 143 (15.50%).

Table 5: The Survivor function for the Patients by Gender

Gender	Mean	Std. Error	95% CI	
			LL	UL
Female	2.333	0.083	2.17	2.495
Male	2.723	0.052	2.62	2.826
Overall	2.624	0.045	2.537	2.712

The sputum conversion event of interest's mean survival time is 2.33 (S.E. = 0.08) for females and 2.72 (S.E. = 0.05) for males, according to the aforementioned table. The average lifespan of a male is longer than that of a female. Male and female TB patients had significantly different survival durations, according to the non-parametric test.

SURVIVAL PLOTS

Typically, survival graphs show cumulative survival, showing a gradual decline in the percentage of patients free of the event. They are occasionally shown as a cumulative survival curve for gender, which depicts the percentage of participants who experience the event over time.

Figure 1.3 Survival curves for TB patients according to gender

Figure 1.4 Cumulative Hazard Function curves for TB patients

Figure 1.5 Kaplan Meier plot for TB patients according to Gender

Figure 1.6 Cumulative Hazard function

Table 6. Treatments might impact TB patients' survival was evaluated using the log-rank method

	χ^2	D.F	P Value
Log Rank	8.805	2	0.012
Breslow	6.559	2	0.038
Tarone-Ware	7.658	2	0.022

The log rank test assesses whether the KM survival curve from two sub population is significant different from each other. How to compare experience of male and female there or more specific how we can compare the survival curve are these two survival curves. We do a log rank test is that the male and female survival curve are equal. We are going to try to see whether there is enough information to reject the null hypothesis. The table value it's showed the log rank test value is ($\chi^2=8.805$, $DF = 2$, $P = 0.012$). P value is indicated there is a significance difference at 5% level. The result reveals that there is a significance difference between in the treatment between treatment-A with control at the same time differences between treatment-B with control.

Table 7. The log-rank test evaluating gender's impact on TB patients' survival

	χ^2	D.F	P Value
Log Rank	16.606	1	0.000
Breslow	24.16	1	0.000
Tarone-Ware	21.935	1	0.000

How can the lives of men and women are compared, or more specifically, how can the survival curves of these two populations be compared? To confirm that the survival curves for men and women are equal, we do a log rank test. We'll attempt to determine whether there is sufficient evidence to disprove the null hypothesis. The log rank test score is represented in the table as ($\chi^2=8.805$, $DF = 2$, $P = 0.012$). The P value indicates that the difference at the 5% level is very significant. The findings demonstrate that male and female survival times differ significantly.

CONCLUSION:

In a survival study, the technique is used to examine patients who got there a particular event and persons who were censored at a particular time. It is also highly useful for contrasting participant groups, that is a treatment group and a control group. Along with the overall comparisons table, other significant and pertinent tables include the Kaplan-Meier estimate curve.

When comparing the survival rates of separate groups, one might compare the cumulative survival at a specific point in time. The drawback of this strategy is that it only compares the survival experiences of the two groups as a whole, rather than across the course of their whole survival experiences. The most common approach for comparing the survival of groups, the log rank test, which takes into account the entire follow-up period, can be used to avoid this issue. The log-rank test deals with the presumption that there are no variations in the probability of an event happening at any particular time between the populations being investigation. Similar presumptions to those of the Kaplan-Meier approach underlie the test.

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